

image created using Google's Gemini

Von OpenStreetMap zu semantisch vernetzten Wissensgraphen

Integration von Community-Geodaten in das Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem

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Session: Daten, Datenbanken und Datenprozessierung

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PROLOG

Zwei Welten?

GIS und Knowledge Graphs sind zwei offene Datenwelten,
die bisher nur wenig verbunden sind

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OpenStreetMap ist strukturierte Community-Daten –
Linked Open Data macht daraus Wissensgraphen

image created using Google's Gemini

Atlas, das Chamäleon, bewegt sich zwischen der Welt von OpenStreetMap und der Welt der Wissensgraphen

AKT 1

Die Welt von OpenStreetMap

image created using Google's Gemini

OpenStreetMap ist eine globale, community-getriebene Geodatenbank

image created using Google's Gemini

OpenStreetMap beschreibt die Welt mit Nodes, Ways, Relations und Tags

image created using Google's Gemini

OpenStreetMap ist stark strukturiert, aber nicht semantisch modelliert

image created using Google's Gemini

OpenStreetMap-Daten sind schwer direkt in Wissensgraphen integrierbar

 Search LinkedGeoData

LinkedGeoData is an effort to add a spatial dimension to the Web of Data / Semantic Web. LinkedGeoData uses the information collected by the OpenStreetMap project and makes it available as an RDF knowledge base according to the Linked Data principles. It interlinks this data with other knowledge bases in the Linking Open Data initiative.

[View it on GitHub](#)

Powered By

The LinkedGeoData Knowledge Base

In order to employ the Web as a medium for data and information integration, comprehensive datasets and vocabularies are required as they enable the disambiguation and alignment of other data and information. Many real-life information integration and aggregation tasks are impossible without comprehensive background knowledge related to spatial features of the ways, structures and landscapes surrounding us.

LinkedGeoData uses the comprehensive OpenStreetMap spatial data collection to create a large spatial knowledge base. It consists of more than 3 billion nodes and 300 million ways and the resulting RDF data comprises approximately 20 billion triples. The data is available according to the Linked Data principles and interlinked with DBpedia and Geo Names.

This site provides information about the LinkedGeoData community project:

- **Datasets** gives an overview about the LinkedGeoData knowledge base and allows to download the whole dataset.
- **Online Access** describes how the data set can be accessed via Linked Data.
- **Use Cases** lists different LinkedGeoData use cases.
- **Publications** gives an overview about LinkedGeoData related publications.
- **Community** explains how the LinkedGeoData community collaborates and how people can contribute to the effort.

via <https://linkedgeo.org/>

Das Projekt "LinkedGeoData" hatte das mal versucht ...

AKT 2

Atlas entdeckt das Semantic Web

via <https://5stardata.info/> and <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

Linked Open Data beschreibt Dinge mit URIs, RDF und Ontologien

Im Semantic Web wird Wissen als Tripel gespeichert

Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Ontologien geben Daten Bedeutung und Struktur

label — **Phaistos disc** (Q465338) — **item identifier**

description — inscribed tablet found in Crete
Phaistos Disk | Phaistos Disc
▶ In more languages — **aliases**

Statements

property — **inception** — **value** **1700 BCE** — **qualifiers**

earliest date	1700 BCE
latest date	1100 BCE
sourcing circumstances	circa
reason for preferred rank	preferred determination method

rank — **▼ 1 reference** — **opened reference**

stated in	Le pouvoir de l'écrit
author	Louis Godart
page(s)	206

+ add reference

statement group — **1400 BCE** — **collapsed reference**

end time	1970
start time	1959

▶ 1 reference + add value

property — **location of discovery** — **value** **Phaistos** — **statement group**

▶ 0 references + add reference + add (statement)

Mtrognitz, CCO, via Wikimedia Commons

Wikibases speichern und erweitern die erzeugten Wissensgraph-Daten

Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALL-E

Knowledge Graphs verknüpfen Daten über Domänen hinweg

Wikibase / Query Service Examples

Query Helper ×

+ Filter

+ Show

Limit

[Query source](#)

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wdqs: <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql>
4
5 SELECT DISTINCT ?CIIC81Label ?3D_view ?wd_id ?OSM_id ?SMRS_id ?LOD_id ?Factgrid_id WHERE {
6   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
7   VALUES ?CIIC81 {tib:Q1407}
8   ?Media_item tib:P63 ?CIIC81.
9   ?Media_item tib:P74 ?3D_view.
10  ?CIIC81 tib:P107 ?wd_id.
11
12  BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(wd:), ?wd_id)) AS ?wd_item)
13
14  SERVICE wdqs: {
15    ?wd_item wdt:P11693 ?OSM_id;
16            wdt:P4057 ?SMRS_id;
17            wdt:P2888 ?LOD_id;
18            wdt:P8168 ?Factgrid_id.
19  }
20 }
21

```

1 result in 513 ms </> Code

CIIC81Label	3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id
Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148----	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081	Q1000294

Föderierte Abfragen verbinden verteilte Wissensgraphen

AKT 3

Die Transformation (osm2lod)

Wie werden OpenStreetMap-Daten zu Linked Open Data?

osm2lod - Architektur und Ontologie

osm2lod - Ontology Scheme

Der **osm2lod** Workflow transformiert OSM-Daten in RDF

Phase I - OSM fetch & RDF export

Phase II - Ontology & ChangeLog

Phase III - Diff vs “Metadata” Wikibase

SPARQL macht die Daten wieder abfragbar

QGIS und Jupyter ermöglichen die Analyse der Wissensgraph-Daten

AKT 4

Use Cases

image created using Google's Gemini

OpenStreetMap-Objekte werden zu Wissensgraph-Entitäten

AKT 4.1

Ogham-Steine aus OpenStreetMap werden zu archäologischen Entitäten im Wissensgraphen

CIIC 178

- Coumeenole North / Dunmore Head
- OSM: node/5145413640
- Wikidata: Q70892682
- SMR: KE052-059002-

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Knoten: CIIC 178
(5145413640)

Version #10

ref:IEsmr requires heritage=2

Bearbeitet vor über 1 Jahr von geozeisig
Änderungssatz #159661420
Standort: 52.1102541, -10.4731829

Tags

heritage	2
heritage:operator	IEsmr
historic	ogham_stone
inscription	ERC MAQI MAQI- ERCIAS MU DOVINIA
moved	no
name	CIIC 178
project	ogham.link
ref:IEsmr	KE052-059002-
source	survey
wikidata	Q70892682
wikimedia_commons	File:Coumeenole_Og ham_Stone_(Dunmore _Head).jpg

↑ Ogham in 3D Project, DIAS,
CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland

OSM to LOD - Beispiel Ogham CIIC 178

[Ausführen](#)
[Teilen](#)
[Export](#)
[Wizard](#)
[Style](#)
[Speichern](#)
[Laden](#)
[Einstellungen](#)
[? Hilfe](#)
overpass turbo
Karte
Daten

```

1 [out:json][timeout:25];
2 {
3   area(3600062273)->.roi;
4   area(3600163393)->.ni;
5 };
6 {
7   nr(area.roi)["historic"="ogham_stone"];
8   nr(area.ni)["historic"="ogham_stone"];
9 };
10 out meta geom;

```

Node 5145413640

Tags 11

- heritage = 2
- heritage:operator = ic:smr
- historic = ogham_stone
- inscription = ERC 1902 1902-ERC144 NU DOV202A
- monu = no
- name = CIIC 578
- project = ogham-link
- ref:it:smr = KE663-053002-
- source = survey
- wikidata = Q78692682
- wikimedia_commons = File:Commons:Ogham_stone_(Dunmore_Head).jpg

Metadata

- timestamp = 2024-11-27T14:04:08Z
- version = 82
- changeset = 398661620
- user = geonitig
- uid = 48370

Coordinates

62.1102641 ; -10.4731923 (other)

© Leaflet © OpenStreetMap contributors
 gpxfile - Nodes: 100, Ways: 1, Relations: 0
 angebot - POIs: 108, Lines: 0, Polygone: 1

OverPassTurbo Query - Ogham

```

SPARQL_OGHAM = """
PREFIX osm2lod: <http://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/osm2lod/>
PREFIX geosparql:<http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>
PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>

SELECT ?item ?label ?wkt ?osmurl ?wd
WHERE {
  ?item a osm2lod:OghamStone ;
    geosparql:hasGeometry ?geom .
  ?geom geosparql:asWKT ?wkt .
  OPTIONAL { ?item rdfs:label ?label . FILTER(lang(?label) = "en") }
  OPTIONAL { ?item foaf:primaryTopic ?osmurl }
  OPTIONAL { ?item owl:sameAs ?wd .
    FILTER(STRSTARTS(STR(?wd), "http://wikidata.org/")) }
}
ORDER BY ?label
"""

og_rows = []
for r in GRAPHS["ogham"].query(SPARQL_OGHAM):
    lat, lon = parse_wkt(r.wkt)
    og_rows.append({
        "label": str(r.label) if r.label else "(unnamed)",
        "lat": lat, "lon": lon,
        "osm_url": str(r.osmurl) if r.osmurl else "",
        "wikidata": str(r.wd) if r.wd else "",
    })

df_og = pd.DataFrame(og_rows).dropna(subset=["lat", "lon"])
print(f"Ogham Stones: {len(df_og)} items | "
      f"{df_og['wikidata'].astype(bool).sum()} linked to Wikidata")

```

Ogham Stones: 107 items | 58 linked to Wikidata

Jupyter Notebook Query - Ogham

http://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/osm2lod/node_5145413640

The CIIC 178 resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorns OGS Plugin

Search: Go **Download options:** Format: **Turtle (TTL)** Download

Property	Value
supportType	ogham (xsd:string)
ontag_historic	ogham_stone (xsd:string)
ontag_name	CIIC 178 (xsd:string)
ontag_source	survey (xsd:string)
ontag_wikidata	Q7092882 (xsd:string)
ontag_wikimedia_commons	File:Comeenoolie_Ogham_Stone_Dunmore_Head.jpg (xsd:string)
hasGeometry (geo:hasGeometry)	5145413640_geom (xsd:string) (xsd:string)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dataset (rdf:type) [1] 422_Human_Made_Object (crm:422_Human_Made_Object) [1] Geometry (xsd:string) [1] OghamStone (xsd:string)
label (rdfs:label)	CIIC 178 (rdf:langString) (xsd:string)
name (owl:sameAs)	ogham178 (xsd:string) [1]
primaryTopic (foaf:primaryTopic)	5145413640 (xsd:string) [1]
is member of (rdfs:member) of	422_Human_Made_Object Instances Collection (xsd:string) [1]
is dataset (rdf:type) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dataset Instances Collection (xsd:string) [1] Geometry Instances Collection (xsd:string) [1] OghamStone Instances Collection (xsd:string) [1]

Metadata

Property	Value
created (terms:created)	2025-12-21T09:33:36.813143+00:00 (xsd:date/Time)
identifier (terms:identifier)	osm:node/5145413640 (xsd:string)
isPartOf (terms:isPartOf)	OSM Overpass Export (xsd:string) [1]
isDataset (terms:isDataset)	osm:node (xsd:string) [1]

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https://www.research-squirrel-engineers.com/

SPARQLing Unicorn HTML Visualisierung

AKT 4.2

*Heilige Quellen werden von
OSM-Features zu semantischen Orten*

Fiachre's Well

- **Saint Fiachre's Well, Freshford**
- **OSM: node/8515265450**
- **Wikidata: Q121842432**
- **SMR: KK020-050004**

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Knoten: Saint
Fiachre's Well
(8515265450)

Version #9

refl:Esmr requires heritage=2

Bearbeitet vor über 1 Jahr von geozeisig

Änderungssatz #160155386

Standort: 52.6216672, -7.1978959

Tags

description	In a hollow, sheltered by an outcrop of natural rock. Steps leading into the underground chamber. Access via driveway into Sheastown House from R700 on the last Sunday in August around 3pm and the 9 days before in the evening during the novena.
heritage	2
heritage:operator	I:Esmr
name	Saint Fiachre's Well
name:etymologywikidata	Q953927
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
refl:Esmr	KK020-050004
service_times	Aug Su[-1]
source	British war office map:SMR:survey
subject:wikidata	Q953927
survey:date	2023-08-25
urls:sketchfab	https://skfb.ly/pq67u
wikidata	Q121842432
wikimedia_commons	Category:St Fiachra's Well, Sheastown

↑ Anne-Karoline Distel, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

↑ b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via https://skfb.ly/oWwIB


```

SPARQL_HOLYWELLS_MAP = """
PREFIX osm2lod: <http://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/osm2lod/>
PREFIX geosparql:<http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>
PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>

SELECT ?item ?label ?wkt ?osmur1 ?denomination ?wd
WHERE {
  ?item osm2lod:exportType "holywells" ;
    geosparql:hasGeometry ?geom .
  ?geom geosparql:asWKT ?wkt .
  OPTIONAL { ?item rdfs:label ?label . FILTER(lang(?label) = "en") }
  OPTIONAL { ?item foaf:primaryTopic ?osmur1 }
  OPTIONAL { ?item osm2lod:osmtag_denomination ?denomination }
  OPTIONAL { ?item owl:sameAs ?wd .
    FILTER(STRSTARTS(STR(?wd), "http://wikidata.org/")) }
}
"""

def parse_wkt(wkt_str):
    """Extract (lat, lon) from '<CRS> POINT(lon lat)' string."""
    m = re.search(r"POINT\(\([\d.\-]+\)\s+\([\d.\-]+\)\)", str(wkt_str))
    if m:
        lon, lat = float(m.group(1)), float(m.group(2))
        return lat, lon
    return None, None

hw_rows = []
for r in GRAPHS["holywells"].query(SPARQL_HOLYWELLS_MAP):
    lat, lon = parse_wkt(r.wkt)
    hw_rows.append({
        "label": str(r.label) if r.label else "(unnamed)",
        "lat": lat,
        "lon": lon,
        "osm_url": str(r.osmur1) if r.osmur1 else "",
        "denomination": str(r.denomination) if r.denomination else "unknown",
        "wikidata": str(r.wd) if r.wd else ""
    })

df_hw = pd.DataFrame(hw_rows).dropna(subset=["lat", "lon"])
print(f"Holy Wells: {len(df_hw)} items with coordinates")

```

Holy Wells: 734 items with coordinates

Jupyter Notebook Query - Holy Wells

AKT 4.3

***Höhlen werden zu geowissenschaftlichen
und archäologischen Fundorten***

Franchthi Cave

- Franchthi Cave, Griechenland
- OSM: [node/1221172611](#)
- Wikidata: [Q1441331](#)

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

↑ Zde, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

↑ Zde, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Knoten: Franchthi Cave (1221172611)

Version #8

(kein Kommentar)

Bearbeitet vor etwa 2 Monaten von NikosSkouteris
Änderungssatz #178017325
Standort: 37,4224939, 23,1311197

Tags

archaeological_site	settlement
historic	archaeological_site
historic:civilization	prehistoric
name	Σπήλαιο Φράχθι
name:en	Franchthi Cave
wikidata	Q1441331
wikipedia	en:Franchthi Cave

↑ © Xalaros, Attribution, via Wikimedia Commons

▶ Ausführen ◀ Teilen 📄 Export 🔮 Wizard 🎨 Style 💾 Speichern 📂 Laden ⚙️ Einstellungen ❓ Hilfe **overpass turbo** 🗺️ Karte 📄 Daten

```

1 [out:json][timeout:25];
2 (
3   node(337519639);
4   node(369821847);
5   node(1221172611);
6   node(2291668187);
7   node(7778324735);
8   node(8814442373);
9   node(18979178567);
10  node(11187939919);
11  node(11189379895);
12  node(1918839486);
13  relation(9343468);
14  node(13619188868);
15 );
16 out meta geom;

```

Node 1221172611

Tags

- archaeological_site = settlement
- historic:civilisation = prehistoric
- name-en = Franchthi Cave
- wikidata = Q648313
- wikispell = en:Franchthi Cave

Metadata

- timestamp = 2016-02-02T17:35:52Z
- version = 8
- changeset = 17889745
- user = nikoskoutaris
- uid = 697828

Coordinates
 37.4224939 / 23.1311987 (euro)

© Leaflet | © OpenStreetMap contributors
 gebäude - Nodes: 11, Wege: 0, Relationen: 1
 angelegte - POIs: 12, Linien: 0, Polygone: 1

OverPassTurbo Query - CI Sites (Caves)

```

SPARQL_CI = """
PREFIX osm2lod: <http://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/osm2lod/>
PREFIX geosparql: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>
PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>

SELECT ?item ?label ?wkt ?osmurl ?wd ?civilization ?natural
WHERE {
  ?item a osm2lod:CI_Findsport ;
    geosparql:hasGeometry ?geom .
  ?geom geosparql:asWKT ?wkt .
  OPTIONAL { ?item rdfs:label ?label . FILTER(lang(?label) = "en") }
  OPTIONAL { ?item foaf:primaryTopic ?osmurl }
  OPTIONAL { ?item owl:sameAs ?wd .
    FILTER(STRSTARTS(STR(?wd), "http://wikidata.org/")) }
  OPTIONAL { ?item osm2lod:osmtag_historic_civilization ?civilization }
  OPTIONAL { ?item osm2lod:osmtag_natural ?natural }
}
ORDER BY ?label
"""

ci_rows = []
for r in GRAPHS["ci"].query(SPARQL_CI):
    lat, lon = parse_wkt(r.wkt)
    ci_rows.append({
        "label": str(r.label) if r.label else "(unnamed)",
        "lat": lat, "lon": lon,
        "osm_url": str(r.osmurl) if r.osmurl else "",
        "wikidata": str(r.wd) if r.wd else "",
        "civilization": str(r.civilization) if r.civilization else "untagged",
        "natural": str(r.natural) if r.natural else ""
    })

df_ci = pd.DataFrame(ci_rows).dropna(subset=["lat", "lon"])
print(f"CI Findsports: {len(df_ci)} items")
display(df_ci[["label", "civilization", "natural", "wikidata"]].to_html(index=False))

```

CI Findsports: 11 items

Jupyter Notebook Query - CI Sites (Caves)

Grotte de Villars

- **Grotte de Villars, Frankreich**
- **OSM: node/2423303117**
- **Wikidata: Q177657**

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Knoten: Grotte de Villars (2423303117)

Version #6

POI+routes Dordogne

Bearbeitet vor über 1 Jahr von Coucouf

Änderungssatz #153778320

Standort: 45.4425621, 0.7853010

Tags

alt_name	Grotte Préhistorique du Cluzeau
fee	yes
heritage	2
heritage:operator	mhs
mhsinscription_date	1958-12-09
name	Grotte de Villars
natural	cave_entrance
ref:mhs	PA00083067
source:heritage	data.gouv.fr, Ministère de la Culture - 2016
tourism	attraction
website	http://grotte-villars.com
wikidata	Q177657
wikipedia	fr:Grotte de Villars

↑ © Grotte de Villars, via <https://grotte-villars.com/en/the-villars-cave/>

OverPassTurbo Query - SISAL Sites (Stalagmiten als Klimaproxy)

```

SPARQL_SISAL = """
PREFIX osm2lod: <http://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/osm2lod/>
PREFIX geosparql: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>
PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>

SELECT ?item ?label ?wkt ?osmurl ?wd ?natural
WHERE {
  ?item a osm2lod:SisalSite ;
    geosparql:hasGeometry ?geom .
  ?geom geosparql:asWKT ?wkt .
  OPTIONAL { ?item rdfs:label ?label . FILTER(lang(?label) = "en") }
  OPTIONAL { ?item foaf:primaryTopic ?osmurl }
  OPTIONAL { ?item owl:sameAs ?wd .
    FILTER(STRSTARTS(STR(?wd), "http://wikidata.org/")) }
  OPTIONAL { ?item osm2lod:osmtag_natural ?natural }
}
ORDER BY ?label
"""

sisal_rows = []
for r in GRAPHS["sisal"].query(SPARQL_SISAL):
    lat, lon = parse_wkt(r.wkt)
    sisal_rows.append({
        "label": str(r.label) if r.label else "(unnamed)",
        "lat": lat, "lon": lon,
        "osm_url": str(r.osmurl) if r.osmurl else "",
        "wikidata": str(r.wd) if r.wd else "",
        "natural": str(r.natural) if r.natural else "",
    })

df_sisal = pd.DataFrame(sisal_rows).dropna(subset=["lat", "lon"])
print(f"SISAL Sites: {len(df_sisal)} items | "
      f"{df_sisal['wikidata'].astype(bool).sum()} linked to Wikidata")

```

SISAL Sites: 221 items | 64 linked to Wikidata

Jupyter Notebook Query - SISAL Sites (Stalagmiten als Klimaproxy)

AKT 4.4

*Vermessungspunkte (Benchmarks) werden zu
Referenzpunkten im Wissensgraphen*

Albert Bridge

- **Albert Bridge, Glasgow**
- **OSM: node/12923704831**

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Knoten:
12923704831

Version #2

Edit Survey point.

Bearbeitet vor 9 Monaten von b-unicycling
Änderungssatz #167794702
Standort: 55.8527993, -4.2472940

Tags

benchmark	yes
man_made	survey_point
surveydate	2025-06-18
survey_pointstructure	cut
wikimedia_commons	File:Benchmark on Albert Bridge.jpg

↑ Anne-Karoline Distel, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Ausführen Teilen Export Wizard Style Speichern Laden Einstellungen Hilfe **overpass turbo** Karte Daten

```

1 [out:json][timeout:100];
2 {
3   area(3600062273)->.roi;
4   area(3600163193)->.ni;
5   area(3600858446)->.scotland;
6 };
7
8 nwr(area.roi)["man_made"="survey_point"]["benchmark"="yes"]["wikimedia_commons"];
9 nwr(area.ni)["man_made"="survey_point"]["benchmark"="yes"]["wikimedia_commons"];
10 nwr(area.scotland)["man_made"="survey_point"]["benchmark"="yes"]["wikimedia_commons"];
11 };
12 out meta geom;

```

Node 12923704831

Tags 5
 benchmark = yes
 man_made = survey_point
 survey_point = 2021-06-10
 survey_point:structure = cut
 wikimedia_commons = 1:1:1:benchmark on Albert
 bridge.jpg

Metadata
 timestamp = 2025-06-18T10:25:45Z
 version = 1
 changeset = 147794782
 user = In-ukip/313ing
 uid = 1733624

Coordinates
 55.8527993 / 4.247294 (open)

50 km

© Leaflet | © OpenStreetMap contributors
 geodata - Nodes: 21, Ways: 0, Relations: 0
 argesoft - POIs: 21, Lines: 0, Polygons: 0

OverPassTurbo Query - Benchmarks (Ireland/UK)

```

SPARQL_BENCHMARKS = """
PREFIX osm2lod: <http://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/osm2lod/>
PREFIX geosparql: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>

SELECT ?item ?label ?wkt ?osmurl ?commons ?structure ?survey_date
WHERE {
  ?item a osm2lod:Benchmark ;
    geosparql:hasGeometry ?geom .
  ?geom geosparql:asWKT ?wkt .
  OPTIONAL { ?item rdfs:label ?label . FILTER(lang(?label) = "en") }
  OPTIONAL { ?item foaf:primaryTopic ?osmurl }
  OPTIONAL { ?item osm2lod:osmtag_wikimedia_commons ?commons }
  OPTIONAL { ?item osm2lod:osmtag_survey_point_structure ?structure }
  OPTIONAL { ?item osm2lod:osmtag_survey_date ?survey_date }
}
ORDER BY ?label
"""

bm_rows = []
for r in GRAPHS["benchmarks"].query(SPARQL_BENCHMARKS):
    lat, lon = parse_wkt(r.wkt)
    bm_rows.append({
        "label": str(r.label) if r.label else "(unnamed)",
        "lat": lat,
        "lon": lon,
        "osm_url": str(r.osmurl) if r.osmurl else "",
        "commons": str(r.commons) if r.commons else "",
        "structure": str(r.structure) if r.structure else "unknown",
        "survey_date": str(r.survey_date) if r.survey_date else ""
    })

df_bm = pd.DataFrame(bm_rows).dropna(subset=["lat", "lon"])
print(f"Benchmarks: {len(df_bm)} items | "
      f"{df_bm['commons'].astype(bool).sum()} with Wikimedia Commons photo")

```

Benchmarks: 21 items | 21 with Wikimedia Commons photo

Jupyter Notebook Query - Benchmarks (Ireland/UK)

AKT 5

Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem

Community-Daten werden Teil von föderierten Dateninfrastrukturen

Vanessa Liebler / NFDI4Objects
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NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

The German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) consortium **NFDI4Objects** aims to meet the infrastructural needs of researchers and practitioners who work on the **material remains** of around **2.6 million years** of human and environmental history to develop integrated solutions for FAIR and LOUD data across the humanities and natural sciences.

Auch in NFDI4Objects spielt OSM eine Rolle!

EPILOG

Die Botschaft

OSM/GIS	LOD/RDF
Feature	Entity
Tag	Property
Geometry / Simple Feature	GeoSPARQL
Overpass Turbo	SPARQL
Layer	Graph
OSM ID	URI
Schema implizit	Schema explizit

Wir konvertieren nicht Daten – wir übersetzen Datenmodelle

- OpenStreetMap ist strukturierte Community-Geodatenbank
- Linked Open Data bringt URIs, RDF und Ontologien
- osm2lod übersetzt OSM in Wissensgraphen
- SPARQL verbindet verteilte Wissensgraphen
- Community-Daten werden Teil von Forschungsinfrastrukturen
- OpenStreetMap kann Teil des Semantic Web werden

Von Features zu Entitäten

image created using Google's Gemini

Finis!

Thx!

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